

Uporaba NGS tehnik pri žlahtnjenju rastlin: analiza heterogenosti barve semen pri kompozitnih populacijah navadnega fižola (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.)

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Sposobnost prilagajanja na različne okoljske dejavnike, domestikacija in postopki žlahtnjenja so privedli do velike genetske raznolikosti navadnega fižola (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). Slednja predstavlja osnovo za ohranjanje ekosistemov, omogoča prilagajanje spremenljivim razmeram v okolju in ustvarjanje novih sort. Barva semen predstavlja pomemben dejavnik izbire, zato je ključno poznavanje genetskih mehanizmov njene variabilnosti. V naši raziskavi smo se osredotočili na kompozitne populacije navadnega fižola, pri čemer vsako populacijo sestavlja od dva do pet različno obarvanih semen – fenotipov. Izmed 50 kompozitnih populacij navadnega fižola smo izbrali štiri, ki so po prvem letu izkazovale najvišjo stopnjo segregacije, ter še dve standardni sorti. Skupno je bilo na polju okarakteriziranih 19 individualnih fenotipov z uporabo 86 deskriptorjev v dveh zaporednih letih, listi pa so bili vzorčeni za molekularne analize. Izbrane populacije so bile poslana na sekvenciranje celotnega genoma (ang. whole genome sequencing; WGS). Z rezultati WGS smo identificirali več kot 8,6 milijona polimorfizmov posameznih nukleotidov (SNP), pri čemer sta imela kromosoma 4 in 1 največjo gostoto SNP-jev (11 %), kromosoma 3 in 6 pa najmanjšo. Za identifikacijo regij genoma, ki so povezane s spremembo barve semen, smo kompozitne populacije razdelili v dve skupini. Prva je vsebovala standardni sorti Golden Gate in ETNA ter kompozitno populacijo INCBN_03048, kjer po prvem letu kulture ni prišlo do spremembe barve semen, druga pa je vsebovala kompozitne populacije KIS Amand, SRGB_00189 in SRGB_00366, kjer je prišlo do spremembe barve semenske ovojnice. Z orodjema XP-CLR in XP-EHH smo identificirali 118 kandidatnih regij, povezanih s spremembo barve semen, med njimi pa je bilo največ fosfatidilinozitolnih signalnih poti. Poleg regulacijskih in strukturnih elementov rezultati nakazujejo pomembnost mehanizmov celičnega transporta pri pigmentaciji semen. Identifikacija in poznavanje omenjenih regij predstavljata dragoceno informacijo za uporabnost in pomen kompozitnih populacij navadnega fižola predvsem v ekološko usmerjenem žlahtnjenju rastlin.

Ključne besede: navadni fižol, barva semen, kompozitne populacije, žlahtnjenje, WGS

Štiri kompozitne populacije in dve standardni sorti, uporabljene v študiji
Four composite populations and two standard varieties used in this study

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NGS technique applied in plant breeding: analysing seed colour heterogeneity in composite populations of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.)

The ability to adapt to different environmental factors as well as domestication and breeding processes have led to a great genetic diversity of the common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). This diversity is the basis for the preservation of ecosystems, adaptation to changing environmental conditions and the creation of new varieties. Seed colour is an important selection factor, which is why knowledge of the genetic mechanisms of its variability is crucial. In our research, we have focused on composite populations of common bean, where each population consists of two to five differently coloured seeds - phenotypes. From the 50 composite populations of common bean, we selected four that showed the highest level of segregation after the first year and two other standard varieties. A total of 19 individual phenotypes were characterised in the field in two consecutive years using 86 descriptors, and leaves were sampled for molecular analysis. Selected populations were sent for whole genome sequencing (WGS). The WGS results identified more than 8.6 million single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), with chromosomes 4 and 1 having the highest density of SNPs (11%) and chromosomes 3 and 6 the lowest. To identify regions of the genome associated with the change in seed colour, the composite populations were divided into two groups. The first group comprised two standard varieties, Golden_Gate and ETNA, and the composite population INCBN_03048, which did not show any change in seed colour after the first year of cultivation, while the second group comprised the composite populations KIS_Amand, SRGB_00189 and SRGB_00366, which showed a change in seed colour. Using the XP-CLR and XP-EHH tools, we identified 118 candidate regions associated with seed colour change, most of which were phosphatidylinositol signalling pathways. In addition to the regulatory and structural elements, the results show us the importance of cellular transport mechanisms in seed pigmentation. The identification and knowledge of the above-mentioned regions provide valuable information on the usefulness and importance of common bean composite populations, especially in organically orientated plant breeding.

Keywords: common bean, seed colour, composite populations, breeding, WGS